

Machine Learning Based Prediction of Munsell Soil Color Components Using Multi-Sensor Satellite Data

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Abstract: Basic soil maps are essential for describing soil and land characteristics, supporting effective land-use planning, and preventing improper land use. However, traditional soil survey and mapping are time-consuming and labor-intensive. In this context, identifying soil color variation is critical for defining potential soil boundaries. Recent advances in remote sensing and machine learning have enabled the prediction of Munsell soil color components (hue, value, and chroma) and the production of outputs that support detailed soil surveys. This study evaluated the prediction of Munsell soil color components using modern approaches and compared the results with digital soil maps produced at a 1:5,000 scale by traditional methods. Support vector machine (SVM) and random forest (RF) models were trained using color-related features derived from Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, and Landsat-8 satellite data, together with soil-series level digital soil map information. To best represent bare soil conditions, imagery from periods with the lowest NDVI and highest bare soil index values was selected. SVM achieved the highest performance for hue, value, and chroma prediction, with overall accuracy values of 81.6%, 79.1%, and 85.4% and κ values of 0.57, 0.57, and 0.40, respectively, whereas RF performed better in predicting the Munsell color code (OA = 69.4%, κ = 0.52).

Keywords: digital soil mapping; machine learning; munsell soil color scale; remote sensing.

1 Introduction

High-resolution soil mapping is of critical importance for sustainable agriculture and land-use planning. Traditional soil mapping processes, which rely on intensive fieldwork and profile descriptions, are generally time-consuming and costly (Soil Science Division Staff 2017). As a result, Digital Soil Mapping (DSM), which models soil properties using environmental covariates and remote sensing, has emerged as a rapid and cost-effective alternative (Kienast-Brown et al. 2017). Among soil properties, soil color quantified using the Munsell color scale serves as a vital indicator for components such as organic matter and iron oxides, and makes a significant contribution to the delineation of soil series boundaries (Rizzo et al. 2023).

Recent studies have successfully applied machine learning algorithms to estimate soil color and physicochemical properties using large-scale optical satellite data (Sahwan et al. 2018, Rizzo et al. 2023). However, research directly comparing modern machine learning outputs with high-resolution (1:5,000) traditional soil maps is quite limited,

particularly in the Mediterranean climate zone. Furthermore, although optical sensors are widely used, the potential for integrating radar data (e.g., Sentinel-1) to optimise estimates during bare-ground periods has not yet been fully explored.

To address these shortcomings, the present study evaluates the performance of RF and SVM models selected for their robustness to noisy data and ability to generalise effectively with limited data in estimating Munsell soil color components. Within the scope of the study, predictions were generated for a typical Mediterranean study area using spectral indices derived from Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2 and Landsat-8 satellite data. By directly comparing the results with traditional 1:5,000-scale soil maps, the aim was to assess the regional validity and operational value of these modern algorithms under specific environmental conditions.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

The research was conducted at the Aksu-Mandırlar Research and Application Farm, located in Antalya, Türkiye (Figure 1). Located approximately 2 km east of the town of Aksu and covering an area of around 120 ha, the study area is characterised by flat or nearly flat topography, a gentle slope, an average elevation of 7.2 m, and a typical Mediterranean climate.

Figure 8. Study area.

2.2 Methods

The 1:5,000 scale digital soil map produced by Sari et al. (2009) was used as the reference dataset for both the derivation of target classes and the validation of the prediction maps. The dataset was generated from 89 sample points that were automatically distributed within the study area with a minimum spacing of approximately 100 m. For each sample point, band and index values

derived from satellite data were extracted. The target variables were defined as Hue, Value, Chroma, and the Munsell color code. Hue classes were defined as 10Yellow-Red(10YR) and 2.5Yellow(2.5Y), Value classes as 4 and 5, and Chroma classes as 2 and 3. The Munsell color code was modelled as a multiclass variable consisting of the hue-value-chroma combinations observed in the reference map.

To determine the bare soil period, vegetation and soil indices were analysed over a one-year time series. The period between 2 and 8 November 2018, when Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) values were at their lowest and Bare Soil Index 1 and Bare Soil Index 2 values were at their highest, was selected as the optimal time window. For this period, cloud-free Landsat-8 and Sentinel-2 optical images, together with Sentinel-1 radar data acquired within the same date range, were used. Sentinel-1 data were evaluated separately for ascending (ASC) and descending (DSC) orbit scenarios. Spectral indices were calculated in Google Earth Engine and ArcGIS Pro. All datasets were resampled to a common spatial resolution of 10 m using the nearest neighbour method to ensure spatial consistency.

Data preprocessing, variable selection, and modelling procedures were conducted in the R environment using the caret, randomForest, and kernlab packages. For each target variable, Sentinel-1 ASC and DSC orbit modes were first evaluated together with optical, thermal, and derived index variables using a preliminary RF out-of-bag test, and the most suitable radar mode was selected at this stage. Subsequently, two modelling scenarios were established. In the first scenario, only optical, thermal, and derived index variables were used. In the second scenario, the selected radar mode was added to these variables. In both scenarios, variable selection was performed using recursive feature elimination (RFE), after which highly correlated ($r > 0.90$) variables were removed to obtain the final predictor sets.

No fixed train/test split was used during model development. Instead, the 89 sample points were evaluated within a repeated 10-fold cross-validation framework with 5 repeats. In each iteration, approximately 90% of the data were used for training and 10% for validation. The same resampling strategy was also adopted during the RFE procedure. Using the final predictor sets RF and SVM models were trained, hyperparameters were tuned, and prediction maps were then produced for the entire study area.

Model performance was assessed at two levels. First, the model development and hyperparameter tuning process was evaluated through repeated 10-fold cross-validation as an internal validation procedure. Second, the final prediction maps were compared with the reference digital soil map using a pixel-based spatial overlay approach. Overall accuracy and the Kappa index were calculated from the pixel-level confusion matrices derived from this comparison. This overlay-based evaluation was used to assess map-level spatial agreement and should not be interpreted as an independent external test dataset.

To improve model interpretability, a post hoc Shapley Additive Explanations (SHAP) analysis was applied to the best-performing models using the predictor sets selected after RFE. In this way, the relative contributions of the selected variables to model predictions were evaluated, thereby supporting the interpretability of the modelling results.

3 Results

3.1 Predictor selection and model interpretation

Following RFE and subsequent correlation filtering, compact predictor sets were obtained for all target variables. For the Hue component, the selected predictors were Sentinel-2 Band 3 (B3), NDVI, Sentinel-2 Band 8 (B8), Land Surface Temperature (LST), and the Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI). For the Value component, the selected predictors were LST, Sentinel-2 Band 2 (B2), NDVI, Sentinel-2 Band 12 (B12), the Temperature Vegetation Index (TVI), and B8. For the Chroma component, the selected predictors were the Temperature Condition Index (TCI), Sentinel-2 Band 11 (B11), B3, B8, the Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI), and NDMI. For the Munsell color code, the final predictor set comprised B3, LST, the Sentinel-1 Descending Orbit Normalized Soil Moisture Index (DSC-NSMI), B8, TVI, and B12. To improve model interpretation, post hoc SHAP analysis was applied to the best-performing models using the predictor sets selected after RFE. Since the Hue, Value, and Chroma variables each consisted of two classes, their SHAP profiles showed largely similar patterns and were not presented separately in order to avoid repetition. In contrast, the Munsell color code variable, which consisted of four classes, provided a more distinctive and interpretable SHAP profile. Therefore, only the SHAP results for the Munsell color code model are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Class-specific mean absolute SHAP values of the selected predictor variables for the Munsell color code model.

3.2 Classification performance and spatial agreement

As shown in Table 1, the model comparisons revealed that the SVM algorithm was more successful in predicting the Hue, Value and Chroma components, while the RF algorithm demonstrated superior performance in predicting the Munsell color code variable. This indicates that SVM is a more effective method for individual color components, whereas RF is a more suitable method for predicting the composite color code. The maps produced by the best-performing models showed a generally good agreement with the reference soil map (Figure 3). In the Hue map, 2.5Y was dominant in the southern unit, whereas 10YR was more common in the northern unit (Figure 3b, f).

Table 4. Classification performance of RF and SVM models for predicting Hue, Value, Chroma, and Munsell color code.

Target Variable	Model	Overall Accuracy %	Kappa Index (κ)
Hue	RF	80.4	0.54
Hue	SVM	81.6	0.57
Value	RF	78.3	0.56
Value	SVM	79.1	0.57
Chroma	RF	84.9	0.40
Chroma	SVM	85.4	0.40
Munsell color code	RF	69.4	0.52
Munsell color code	SVM	66.8	0.50

In the Value map, class 4 was mainly associated with the northern unit and class 5 with the southern unit (Figure 3d, h). In the Chroma map, class 3 covered most of the study area, while class 2 occurred in more limited zones (Figure 3c, g). For the Munsell color code, the RF model represented the dominant pattern more clearly in the southern unit, whereas the northern unit displayed a more complex class arrangement (Figure 3a, e). Overall, the predicted maps captured the main spatial patterns observed in the reference map, although some local fragmentation was evident in transition areas.

4 Discussion

Figure 3. Reference and predicted maps for the Munsell color code, hue, chroma, and value. Panels a-d present the reference maps, whereas panels e-h present the predicted maps.

The findings indicate that Munsell soil color components can be predicted with relatively high accuracy using remote sensing covariates and machine-learning algorithms. This is consistent with previous studies showing that remote sensing can successfully capture spatial variation in soil color and support soil mapping applications (Sahwan et al. 2018, Rizzo et al. 2023). More broadly, the increasing use of machine-learning methods in digital soil mapping highlights their value for modelling spatial soil variability from environmental covariates (Kienast-Brown et al. 2017).

In the present study, SVM performed better for Hue, Value and Chroma, whereas RF was more successful for the composite Munsell color code. This suggests that individual color components and the combined color code

exhibit different classification behaviour. Similar differences among algorithms have been reported in soil mapping studies, where model performance varies according to the predictor set, class structure, and characteristics of the training data (Wadoux et al. 2020). The stronger performance of SVM for the individual components may be related to its ability to generalise well under limited training data, whereas RF appears to be more suitable for the more complex multi-class structure of the Munsell color code (Mountrakis et al. 2011).

The selected predictors retained after RFE, together with the SHAP results for the Munsell color code model, indicate that soil color variation is associated with optical bands, surface temperature, moisture, and vegetation-related conditions. In this respect, the combined use of Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, and Landsat-8 data improved the representation of surface and pedological properties affecting soil color. However, the limited sample size, class imbalance, and relatively small study area constitute important limitations. Future studies should therefore test the approach with larger and more balanced datasets, multi-temporal imagery, and higher-resolution or hyperspectral data.

5 Conclusions

This study has demonstrated that remote sensing data and machine learning algorithms can be effectively utilised in the estimation of Munsell soil color components. The findings revealed that SVM performed better for the Hue, Value and Chroma variables, whilst RF were more successful in estimating the Munsell color code, thereby demonstrating that individual color components and the composite color code have different modelling requirements.

The combined use of Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2 and Landsat-8 data has contributed to the incorporation of different pedological and surface characteristics of soil color into the model, and has demonstrated the applicability of remote sensing-supported approaches for digital soil mapping. Although the method does not replace detailed field surveys, it provides a useful tool for rapid preliminary assessment, sampling planning and the identification of potential soil boundaries.

However, testing the approach across larger areas, different spatial patterns and data from varying time periods is important for a more comprehensive assessment of the method's generalisability.

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